

CHOOSING/ADAPTING/DEVELOPING ESP MATERIALS IN IT AND ECONOMY FIELDS

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Annotation: When creating tailor-made materials for economy and finance students to learn English, it is important to focus on language skills and vocabulary relevant to their field of study. Here are some examples of how to develop materials specifically tailored to economy and finance students learning English

Key words: Relevance and authenticity, learner needs and goals, adaptability, practicality

1 INTRODUCTION

The field of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) teaching requires careful consideration when it comes to selecting, adapting, or developing appropriate teaching materials. This presentation explores the challenges encountered in this process and offers strategies to overcome them effectively.

Importance of Materials

-Materials play a vital role in ESP teaching and learning.

- They provide the necessary language input and serve as a guide for language instruction.

- Well-designed materials can greatly improve student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes.

Factors to Consider

-Relevance and authenticity

-Learner needs and goals

-Adaptability

-Practicality

There are various sources for ESP materials, such as textbooks, articles, online resources, and authentic materials from the learners' field.

2 MANUSCRIPT REPARATION:

When choosing existing materials, consider their relevance, suitability, and adaptability to your teaching context and learners' needs.

- It is also essential to incorporate a variety of materials to cater to different learning styles and preferences.

- Adapting materials allows for customization to better suit the learners' needs and goals.

- Creating your own materials can be time-consuming but allows for complete customization.

- Consider making changes to the language input, tasks, and activities to better align with the learners' field and level.

- Be mindful of copyright and always give credit to the original source.

- Start by analyzing the language needs and goals of your learners and identifying the specific language skills and vocabulary required.

- Use a variety of sources for inspiration and incorporate authentic materials whenever possible.

When creating tailor-made materials for economy and finance students to learn English, it is important to focus on language skills and vocabulary relevant to their field of study. Here are some examples of how to develop materials specifically tailored to economy and finance students learning English:

1. Financial News Analysis

2. Case Studies

3. Business English Vocabulary

4. Financial Reports and Statements

5. Presentation and Public Speaking Skills

6. Academic Writing in Economics and Finance

7. Business Etiquette and Negotiation Skills

7. Authentic Speaking Activities

By developing tailor-made materials for IT students and economy and finance students learning English, instructors can ensure that the content is relevant, engaging, and directly applicable to their future careers.

When creating tailor-made materials for IT students to learn English, it is important to design content that is relevant to their field of study and focuses on the language skills and vocabulary they will need in their professional careers. Here are some examples of how to develop materials specifically tailored to IT students learning English:

1. Technical Vocabulary Worksheets

2. Reading Comprehension on IT Topics

3. Listening Exercises with IT Audio Materials

4. Role-Play Scenarios

5. Writing Assignments on IT Projects

6. Grammar Exercises with IT Context

3 CONCLUSIONS

Choosing, adapting, and developing materials for ESP requires careful consideration of various factors.

-The ultimate goal is to provide relevant, authentic, and practical materials that cater to the learners' specific language needs and goals.

- With the right materials, we can create a more engaging, effective, and enjoyable learning experience for our ESP students.

Use of information technologies at lessons creates unique possibility of creation of the natural language environment during the work on the project for independent information search, for enrichment of a lexicon, grammar check. Thus, problem teaching teaches children to get knowledge independently.

In summary it should be noted that problem teaching stimulates personal activity of pupils, and it provides the active relation to knowledge, persistence of pupils, and, certainly positive result in training and education. Pupils become more sociable, are able to prove the point of view, find the way of expression of thoughts and feelings.

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